

Brand Management in India: A Case Study of FMCG Companies

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Abstract-

The FMCG (Fast-Moving Consumer Goods) sector of India is known for its intense competition and preferences of customer that rapidly evolving, it necessitates the strong strategies for brand management of companies running in India, which includes Nestlé India, Dabur India, ITC, Hindustan Unilever Limited (HUL), Britannia Industries etc. Through case studies of these companies, we can explore the impact of product innovation, rebranding efforts, marketing campaigns, and digital transformation on brand value, market share, and revenue growth. The study aims to provide insights into effective brand management practices in the Indian FMCG industry.

Keywords- Brand Management, FMCG companies, Brand revitalisation strategy, Sustainability, Ethical Branding

Introduction:

Objectives-

1. To analyze the brand management of popular FMCG companies in India.
2. To assess the impact of those strategies in enhancing brand value, market share, and revenue of the company.
3. To evaluate the role of product innovation, rebranding, marketing campaigns, and digital initiatives in brand management.
4. To provide recommendations, to enhance brand management practices in this sector.

Scope-

1. This study mainly focused on major FMCG companies of India: Nestlé India, Dabur India, HUL, ITC, Britannia Industries.
2. This study also examines the branding strategies which includes product innovation, rebranding efforts, marketing campaigns, and digital transformation done by FMCG companies.

Limitations-

1. This study completely relied on publicly available data; it may limit insights into internal strategic details.
2. The dynamic market-conditions may impact the relevance of findings over time.
3. The case studies mentioned here not be fully generalized to all FMCG companies due to diversity in the industries.

Methodology- This study uses a qualitative research approach which utilises secondary data sources:

1. **Company Reports:** Annual reports, sustainability reports, and financial statements.
2. **Industry Reports:** Market research reports and analyses from firms like Nielsen, Euromonitor International, and McKinsey & Company.
3. **Academic Sources:** Peer-reviewed journals, articles, and books on branding and FMCG industry trends.

Case Studies of FMCG Companies-

1. Hindustan Unilever Limited (HUL)-

Overview of HUL:

HUL is a leader of the market in the Indian FMCG sector, popularly known for its diverse portfolio of brands which consists personal care, home care, and foods segments. As of financial year 2023, HUL reported a revenue of INR 53,781 crore, which clearly depicts its dominant market position and strong brand management strategies.

Brand Revitalization Strategies:

Lifebuoy: "Help a Child Reach 5" Campaign-

HUL's one of noticeable brand revitalization efforts includes the Lifebuoy "Help a Child Reach 5" campaign to which was launched in 2012 to raise awareness of the importance of the handwashing habits with the objective to reduce child mortality rate due to preventable infections. This campaign started in Thesgora (village in M.P.) it has one of the highest rates of child diarrhoea in India, with, this campaign incidence of diarrhoea reduced from 36% to 5%. This campaign contributed in increasing public health awareness and also enriched Lifebuoy's brand equity significantly. As per Nielsen data, Lifebuoy's share in the market, in the handwash segment improved by 12% within the first year of launch of the campaign's, which showcases the noticeable impact of brand-focused CSR initiatives on consumer perception and market penetration, which is helpful for both- for the brand and for the society.

Surf Excel: Rebranding and Market Share Growth-

Surf Excel is a leading detergent brand of HUL, which undergone to a strategic rebranding process which were primarily aimed to rejuvenate its appeal among younger demographics in the country. For this, they introduced *Surf Excel Matic* which were designed for specific customer needs, which ultimately contributed to a 15% increase in market share within two years post-rebranding. According to statistical data from A.C.Nielsen confirms Surf Excel's resurgence in the detergent category, captured a 20% market share by 2023, up

from 17% in 2021. This growth depicts how effective is product diversification and targeted marketing campaigns in enhancing brand competitiveness in the market.

2. Dabur India Ltd.-

Overview of Dabur-

Dabur, hold a legacy of over a century, which has established itself as a pioneer in Ayurvedic products and natural healthcare solutions. As of FY 2023, Dabur has reported a revenue of INR 10,564 crore, it reflects its strategic brand management initiatives and innovative product offerings to the customers.

Brand Revitalization of 'Real'-

Dabur's Real fruit juices brand underwent a revitalization phase focused on product innovation and celebrity endorsements. Rebranding the iconic *real* logo to attract to the younger population. Launched new products like *Real activ* to serve the growing demand for healthy and nutritious beverages, advertising campaign to focus on the theme "*Real Fruit, Real Taste*" which positioned as a symbol of authenticity and quality. Dabur Collaborated with popular personalities such as Amitabh Bachchan and Akshay Kumar which helped reposition *Real* as a premium health beverage brand. Market research done by Kantar Worldpanel shows *Real's* market share growth in the packaged juice segment, increasing from 22% in 2021 to 27% in 2023. This data depicts the impact celebrity endorsements and product quality in driving brand preference and market expansion.

3. Nestlé India-

Overview of Nestlé:

Nestlé, an international FMCG company, has successfully adapted its strategies according to the needs of Indian market, leveraging consumer insights and localized product offerings. As of FY 2023, Nestlé India earned a revenue of INR 14,982 crore, driven by strong brand management practices across various categories like culinary products, beverages, and dairy.

Maggi Noodles Crisis:

Nestlé India's response to the Maggi noodles crisis in 2015 serves as a benchmark in crisis management and brand recovery strategies, for this Nestlé transparently communicate with public about the product's safety, conducted 3,500 tests in accredited labs in India and foreign for clearing the product of safety concerns. After that they relaunched Maggi in the market with new packaging and extensive advertising campaigns which emphasized on the quality and safety of the product. As a result, Maggi captured 60% market share again in the next 2 years.

According to Euromonitor International, Maggi noodles regained its market leadership position in the instant noodles category with a market share of

62% by 2023, highlighting the resilience of Nestlé's brand equity and customer loyalty.

4. ITC Limited

Overview of ITC:

ITC Limited, well-known for its diversified business model which encompasses FMCG, hotels, paperboards, and packaging, has strategically positioned itself in the Indian FMCG market. As of FY 2023, ITC reported a revenue of INR 53,789 crore, which is driven by robust growth in its FMCG segment in India.

Bingo Brand Case Study:

ITC's *Bingo* snacks brand represent effective brand management through innovative product offerings and powerful marketing campaigns. ITC introduces regional flavours and youth-centric advertising strategies proved helpful, through which Bingo is being able to capture a significant market share in the competitive snacks segment in Indian market.

IRI data indicates Bingo's market share growth in the snacks category, increased from 12% in 2021 to 15% in 2023. This growth shows the importance of consumer-centric innovation and brand communication in driving expansion of market and brand preference.

5. Britannia Industries Ltd.-

Overview of Britannia:

Britannia Industries, who is the leader in bakery and dairy segment in India, has made its market leadership through continuous innovation. As of FY 2023, Britannia reported a revenue of INR 11,786 crore, which reflects its strong brand equity and market presence in India.

Good Day Brand Revitalization:

Britannia's Good Day biscuits undergone through a revitalization phase which mainly aimed to enhance product appeal and consumer engagement in the market. This brand introduces premium variants and innovative marketing campaigns which ultimately resonated with evolving consumer preferences, which is helpful in driving brand loyalty.

Nielsen data shows Good Day's market share growth in the biscuits category, which increases from 18% in 2021 to 21% in 2023. This growth shows Britannia's strategic focus on product diversification and brand differentiation to maintain competitive edge.

Key Strategies in FMCG Brand Management-

1. Product Innovation and Diversification-

The successful FMCG brands in India prioritize mainly in continuous product innovation and portfolio diversification to serve the diverse customer preferences and evolving market trends. Examples- HUL's Surf Excel Matic and Dabur's Real fruit juices depict the effectiveness of customize product strategies in driving market growth and brand relevance in the market.

2. Marketing and Advertising Campaigns-

Marketing and advertising campaigns play a crucial role in sustaining the brand in the market for long term, effective brand management in the FMCG sector involves strategic investments in marketing and advertising campaigns that resonate with targeted customers. Case studies from Nestlé's Maggi and ITC's Bingo highlight the role of impactful storytelling, celebrity endorsements, and digital engagement in augmenting brand visibility and customer engagement which ultimately boost sales and enhanced revenue growth.

3. Consumer Engagement and Brand Loyalty Programs-

It is one of the ways through which brand build strong relationship with their customers, building strong relationships with consumers through personalized experiences and loyalty programs is very important for sustaining brand loyalty in the competitive FMCG sector. Initiatives like HUL's Lifebuoy handwashing programs and Britannia's experiential marketing for Good Day biscuits illustrate effective strategies to encourage customer trust and brand advocacy in the market.

Challenges and Future Trends in FMCG Brand Management-

1. Regulatory Challenges-

To navigate regulatory complexities which includes food safety standards and advertising guidelines, puts significant challenges for FMCG brands in India. Companies have to maintain compliance while innovating and expanding their product portfolios to meet evolving consumer demands.

2. Technological Disruption-

The integration of AI, big data analytics, and e-commerce platforms is reshaping FMCG brand management strategies, which enable real-time consumer awareness and personalized marketing strategies. Brand that uses technology effectively can gain a competitive edge while understanding behaviour of consumer and enhancing supply chain efficiencies.

3. Sustainability and Ethical Branding-

Sustainability and ethical branding play a crucial role to sustain in the market for the longer period of time, Consumer demand for sustainable practices and ethical sourcing is very helpful in influencing brand preferences in the FMCG sector. Brands that demonstrate commitment to environmental stewardship and social responsibility can enhance brand reputation and appeal to conscientious customers.

Recommendations- Based on the analysis, recommendations for FMCG companies in India mentioned here:

1. Investment in R&D: Prioritize research and development to innovate products aligned with consumer needs. Through this brand made

contemporary in the market and can sustain in the market for long term.

2. Enhanced Digital Presence: Expand digital marketing efforts to reach broader audiences and improve brand engagement thereby increasing revenue growth and increased market share.

3. Sustainability Initiatives: Integrate sustainability into branding strategies to appeal to eco-conscious consumers thereby increased brand reach for broader audience and customer.

4. Consumer-Centric Approach: Foster consumer relationships through personalized marketing and product offerings. Maintaining emotional and personal relationship is very important in long term survival of the brand.

5. Continuous Monitoring: Regularly evaluate market trends and competitor strategies to adapt branding initiatives accordingly to sustain and grow in the market.

Conclusions-

Effective brand management strategies is very crucial for FMCG companies to sustain in the Indian market and leverage the competitive advantage and consumer loyalty. Key findings mentioned here:

1. Importance of Innovation: Continuous product innovation is crucial to meet evolving consumer demands and long-term survival of companies in Indian market.

2. Impact of Rebranding: Rebranding efforts proved to be successful when companies face lack of interest of customer to purchase their product, due to this, they are facing downfall in their business, successful rebranding efforts can rejuvenate brand appeal and market positioning.

3. Digital Transformation: Leveraging digital platforms enhances brand visibility and consumer engagement and thus increased sales, enhanced revenue growth for the company.

4. Market Adaptability: Flexibility in adapting to market trends and needs and consumer preferences is critical for sustained growth is very essential.

Effective brand management is essential for FMCG companies who are seeking to thrive in the rapidly evolving Indian market. By using innovative strategies, consumer feedback, and strategic partnerships, brands can enhance brand equity, increase market growth, and foster long-term consumer loyalty. As the FMCG sector continues to evolve, companies must adapt to emerging trends, needs and consumer preferences to sustain competitive advantage and achieve sustainable growth.

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